

Employee Engagement in Ethiopia as a Result of Corporate Ethos

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Abstract – This study's goal is to evaluate the impact of corporate culture on employee engagement. The researchers adopted a quantitative research strategy while using an explanatory research design. Stratified Random Sampling Technique was used to select 245 respondents from across all strata as sample respondents using the probability sampling methodology. A structured, self-administered questionnaire was created to gather data from respondents, and 230 questionnaires were used in total. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyse the data. Pearson According to correlation analysis, there was a statistically significant positive association between workers' engagement and each of the four corporate ethos components (i.e., involvement, consistency, flexibility, and mission). Additionally, compared to the other dimensions, adaptability had a stronger positive and statistically significant correlation with worker engagement. Additionally, compared to the other dimensions, adaptability had a stronger positive correlation and statistical significance with workers engagement. However, mission had a beneficial but statistically insignificant impact on employee engagement. In light of this, the investigators advise maintaining the corporate ethos with a significant contribution to engagement by enhancing workers in decision-making and rewarding innovation to encourage workers for further creativity.

Keywords: Corporate ethos, Workers Engagement, Educational Workforce.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the late 2010s and early 2020s, there have been numerous definitions of the term "corporate ethos" (Okocha, 2022). Edgar Schein Model, Deal and Kennedy Model, and Charles Handy Model are three popular corporate ethos models that Dolan and Lingham (2020) enumerated. Corporate ethos was defined by Denison and Neale (2011) as "the underlying values, beliefs and principles that serve as a foundation for an organization's management system, as well as the set of management practices and behaviors that both exemplify and reinforce those basic principles" (Adula et al., 2022). Involvement, consistency, flexibility, and mission are the four corporate ethos elements that Denison's model illustrates and that were taken into account for this study.

Affective Engagement, Continuance Engagement, and Normative Engagement were all included in Allen and Meyer's (2018) three-part engagement model. The term "affective engagement" relates to employees' emotional ties to, identification with, and participation in the company. According to various researchers' findings in their individual studies, corporate ethos positively influences employee engagement and tends to increase employees' loyalty to their employer (Asghar, Mojtaba, and Sadeghi, 2021; Ghader and Afkhami, 2021; Habib et al., 2021; Coffey, Trew, and Trigunarsyah, 2020; Wakjira, & Kant, 2022). Masoumeh & Alliahyari's (2022) and Asefa & Kant (2022) founded a strong association between corporate ethos and employees' engagement with the organisation lends further weight to this.

This study's goal is to determine which aspects of corporate ethos have a significant impact on workers' engagement in the educational workforce at Bule Hora University. This is done in light of the concept of corporate ethos and workers engagement, as well as the positive relationship between corporate ethos and organisational engagement asserted by various researchers..

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Any institution's success depends significantly on its highly dedicated faculty and staff (Ahmad, 2022). However, research on the organisational engagement of educational workers on the African continent is reportedly quite scarce (Fako et al., 2021). Accordingly, Abebe and Markos (2022) discovered that the educational workforce at Ethiopian universities is not very committed for a variety of reasons, including the institution's standards, vision, missions, and objectives not being in line with the worker. According to Abebe & Markos (2022) and Kenesa Kebede et al., (2023) developing a corporate culture is essential to adapting any organisation to the shifting needs and demands of the global marketplace.

Accordingly, various authors and researchers claimed that corporate ethos has a favourable and significant impact on workers engagement. A study by Asghar, Mojtabaand, Sadeghi (2021); Ghader and Afkhami (2021); Azadi, Bagheri, Eslami and Aroufzad (2020) depicted that there is significant relationship between corporate ethos and workers engagement. They used Denison's corporate ethos model to draw this conclusion.

On the other hand, a study by Nongo and Ikyanyon (2020) showed that while some corporate ethos metrics have an impact on worker engagement, others do not. Corporate ethos is crucial in boosting the level of worker engagement to the organisation. Therefore, these researchers draw the conclusion that organisational engagement is not significantly correlated with consistency or mission, two aspects of the corporate ethos listed on the Denison Model..

However, according to Bizuneh, M. (2022), the most important factor for employee engagement is adaptability, which is followed by involvement and mission. Consistency doesn't, however, significantly affect employee engagement. Getachew (2022) and Wakjira, & Kant (2023) also demonstrates the beneficial but statistically negligible impact that consistency and involvement have on employee engagement. Researchers started looking into these issues in-depth by performing a real study because of the inconsistencies in the conclusions of various researchers and evidence gaps.

1.2 Research Objective

- To evaluate the various corporate ethos of Bule Hora University's educational workforce.
- To research the connections between different corporate ethos and worker engagement in Bule Hora University's educational workforce.
- To examine the effects of various corporate ethos on worker engagement in Bule Hora University's educational workforce.

2. EMPIRICAL REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1.1 Consequence of Corporate ethos on worker Engagement

Although corporate ethos and employee engagement have been the subjects of the most research in management studies, both ideas continue to elude researchers (Shoaib et al., 2020). Additionally, as shown on the study's problem statement, there is a lack of consistency in the results of studies on the impact of various corporate ethos traits on employee engagement. According to the study's specific goal, the following

paragraphs include research findings from several academics that looked at the impact of corporate ethos (involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission) on employee engagement.

1. Involvement and Worker Engagement

Involvement and engagement have a considerable and favourable link, according to a study by Nongo and Ikyanyon (2020). In a similar vein, Singh & Verghese (2021) discovered a strong positive association between organisational involvement and worker empowerment. Furthermore, Asghar et al, (2021) and Panigrahi et al., (2022) assert that one of the most crucial aspects of corporate ethos is involvement. Additionally, 210 full-time employees of the Iranian bank Saderat Iran participated in a study that revealed a favourable correlation between involvement and worker engagement (Bani et al., 2021). The decision was made about the small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), and the outcome demonstrates that participation and involvement have a significant and favourable relationship (Ezekiel and Darius, 2020).

2. Consistency and Worker Engagement

According to Nongo & Ikyanyon (2020) and Tesfaye et al., (2022), there is no meaningful connection between consistency and engagement. Asghar, Mojtaba, and Sadeghi (2021), Ghader, and Afkhami (2021) and Adula et. al., (2023) on the other hand, found that consistency and organisational engagement have a positive relationship. Hakim (2021) also claimed that stability (consistency) is a sign of what is most powerful in influencing the corporate ethos variable. A positive association between consistency and employee engagement was found, according to an empirical investigation. According to the study's findings (Bani et al. 2021) consistency had a significant impact on employees' engagement. According to a study's findings, there was a favourable, albeit not statistically significant, correlation between consistency and worker engagement (Ezekiel and Darius; 2020; Gobena & Kant, 2022).

3. Adaptability and Worker Engagement

According to the corporate ethos hypothesis, an organisation will adapt to the desired changes and circumstances. This will help employees adjust in a changing environment, increasing their level of engagement (Kant & Asefa, 2022). Similar to this, employees showed the highest levels of engagement when they felt that the company valued learning more (adaptability traits), responded to current trends, and foresaw changes in the future (Ghader & Afkhami, 2021; Asghar et al., 2021). According to an empirical study, engagement and adaptability have a considerable and favourable link (Ezekiel S. and Darius N. 2020). Additionally, a study (Bani et al. 2021) demonstrates a favourable relationship between adaptability and worker engagement. The organisational involvement is positively and significantly impacted by the corporate ethos' adaptability (Sunarsih and Mashithoh, 2022).

4. Mission and Worker Engagement

Denison & Neale (2011) contend that an organization's mission establishes the social function and external aims that give it meaning and purpose. On the other hand, Nongo & Ikyanyon (2020) found no evidence of a connection between engagement and mission. According to a study, there was a strong but unfavourable correlation between workers engagement and mission (Ezekiel and Darius 2020; Tufa, & Kant (2023). Additionally, an empirical study by Adula et al. (2023) and Bani et al. (2021) and Yadete & Kant. (2023) demonstrates that the mission had a significant impact on employee engagement.

2.1.2 Empirical Studies in Ethiopian Perspectives

According to Besha et al., (2021), corporate ethos plays a key role in influencing engagement and performance. Endawoke (2009) attested that OC also had a substantial impact on organisational goals in the Ethiopian environment. Abebe & Markos (2022) and Adula & Kant (2022) discovered that the university's educational staff in Ethiopia is not very devoted and exhibits low levels of engagement. According to the research done by Bizuneh (2022), adaptability is the corporate ethos trait that contributes the most. Additionally, the research by Getachew (2022) and Kant et al., (2022) reveals that employees become more devoted to their employers the more they identify with the company's mission.

Conceptual Framework

Fig -1:Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Description of Study Area

One of Ethiopia's 44 universities is Bule Hora University. As one of the government-run higher education institutions, it was founded in 2003 E.C. The Bule Hora Town campus of this institution is situated 470 km south of Addis Abeba in the West Guji Zone of the Oromia Regional State.

3.2 Research Design

The researchers utilised a descriptive and explanatory research strategy for this study. Descriptive research seeks to accurately depict a person, an event, or a scenario (Robson, 2002). Descriptive formats work better for quantitative research than other forms because the goal of this study is to characterize the behaviour of the subject under study. The researchers gather information, and they find that Bule Hora University employs 960 people in the educational workforce altogether. Of these employees, 636 are working at Bule Hora University while the remaining 324 are on leave to complete their studies. Investigators have opted to only use samples from employees who are currently on the job.

3.2.1 Sampling Technique and Sampling Size

Probability sampling was employed in the investigation. The university colleges were kindly categorised according to their educational fields and samples were selected from each stratum using a systematic selection approach in order to ensure that the population of the study had an equal probability of inclusion. Yamane Taro's 1967 formula Using a 95% probability sample size decision technique

. n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)
n = 636 / (1 + 636(0.05)^2)
n = 245

Table -1.1: Sample size distribution

Table with 7 columns: College or Institute, Population (Male, Female, Total), and Sample drawn (Male, Female, Total). Rows include Engineering and Technology, Natural and Computational Science, Business and Economics, Social science and Humanities, Agricorporate ethos and Life Science, Informatics, Healthy, Educational and Behavioral Science, School of Law, and TOTAL.

Source own survey (2022)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table -1.2: Exploratory Enabler Analysis – KMO and Bartlett's Test

	KayserMeyerOlkin <i>KMO</i>	Bartlett's Test
Involvement	0.847	.000
Consistency	0.836	.000
Adaptability	0.824	.000
Mission	0.849	.000
Affective Engagement	0.890	.000
Continuance Engagement	0.870	.000
Normative Engagement	0.864	.000

Source: SPSS Reliability Test (2022)

Tests by KMO and Bartlett. Two tests that demonstrate whether your data are suitable for structure detection are shown in this table. The proportion of variance in your variables that might be due to underlying factors is indicated by the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy statistic. The Kayser Meyer Olkin KMO coefficient is more than 0.8, as can be seen from table 1.2 above. Overall, it demonstrates that the data are adequate.

Table -1.3: Kruskal-Wallis Test

Enabler of Workers Engagement	Experience Group in years			Chi-square value	P value
	1-3	4-6	7-10		
Involvement	125.05	105.51	147.61	9.070	.011*
Consistency	118.05	104.70	173.22	17.648	.000**
Adaptability	113.43	104.93	185.50	29.110	.000**
Mission	104.95	116.69	139.52	4.687	.096
Workers Engagement	120.40	104.38	168.22	16.823	.000**

Note: ** denotes significant at 1% level

* denotes significant at 5% level

Source own survey (2022)

The aforementioned table shows that there were statistically significant differences between the work experiences of workers in involvement, consistency, adaptability, and workers engagement based on 2 values of 9.070, 17.648, 29.110, and 16.823 with P0.01 respectively. This suggests that employees with fewer job experience—1 to 3 years, 4 to 6 years—are less engaged in the educational workforce than those with 7 to 10 years of experience.

4.2 Assumption of Multicollinearity

Table -1.4: Multicollinearity and independence of residual test

	Collinearity Statistics		Durbin-Watson
	Tolerance	VIF	
Involvement	.394	2.538	1.936
Consistency	.250	3.994	
Adaptability	.367	2.728	
Mission	.487	2.055	

Source own survey (2022)

The tolerance values for each independent variable (involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission) are indicated in the table above and are, respectively, 0.394, 0.250, 0.367, and 0.487, all of which were not less than 0.10. This is further corroborated by the VIF value, which was significantly below 10, at 2.538, 3.994, 2.728, and 4.055, respectively. As a result, the assumption of multicollinearity was not broken by the analysis.

4.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Fig -2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Source owe survey, (2022)

Finding out if observed variables influence latent or unobserved variables requires using both structural equation modelling (SEM) and confirmatory factor analysis. Analysis of several regressions. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) in the aforementioned figure proved that the factor structure of every group of observed variables was more than 0.6, which is the threshold limit. A link between the variables that are seen and the underlying latent constructs can be tested using CFA.

Table -1.5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.572a	.327	.315	.42596

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19.827	4	4.957	27.319	.000a
	Residual	40.825	225	.181		
	Total	60.652	229			

Model		Standardized			T	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Coefficients			
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.708	.177		9.635	.000
	Involvement	.229	.061	.327	3.752	.000
	Consistency	-.095	.074	-.139	-1.275	.203
	Adaptability	.342	.078	.398	4.402	.000
	Mission	.036	.057	.050	.634	.527

Dependent Variable: Worker's Engagement

Source: SPSS Regression results output, 2022

4.4 Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Since their p-values are 0.000 and less than 0.01 ($p < 0.01$), the table above shows that adaptability and involvement contributed statistically significantly to workers' engagement at the 95% level of confidence. However, since consistency and mission both had p-values greater than the significance level of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$) and were statistically insignificant, they had no effect on employee engagement.

Generally speaking, with a p-value of 0.000 and participation coming in second, flexibility is the most important independent variable that statistically significantly contributes to workers' engagement.

Fig -3: Structural Equation Modeling
Source: SEM, AMOS, 2023

The fluctuation and correlation of the observed variables acquired from the provided data in the SEM described above allow for the inference of causation inside the model. The correlation coefficient and standard deviation are typically used to measure association and variance, respectively.

4.5 Hypothesis Testing

To determine if a hypothesis was accepted again or rejected, hypothesis testing is based on standardised coefficients Beta and P-value. With a beta value of 0.327, participation, workers' engagement will grow by 32.7% for every unit increase in involvement. The researchers therefore endorsed the (H1) hypothesis and rejected the (Ho) hypothesis. This shows that involvement positively and statistically significantly influences (contributes to) worker engagement. Consistency has a beta value of () i.e. -0.139, which indicates that if consistency increases by one unit, there will be a 13.9% fall in worker engagement. The researchers therefore accepted (Ho) and rejected (H1) as competing hypotheses. Adaptability According to the beta value (), or 0.398, there will be a 39.8% rise in worker engagement for every unit increase in adaptability. As a result, the researchers endorsed the (H1) hypothesis while rejecting the (Ho) hypothesis. The mission of the organization one unit rise in employees' identification with the organisational mission will result in a 5% increase in employees' engagement, according to the beta value of r 0.050. As a result, the researchers disregarded (H1) and accepted (Ho).

5. CONCLUSIONS

The most important independent variable that significantly affects worker engagement statistically is adaptability. The researchers came to the conclusion that employees are more dedicated to the institution if it can read its surroundings, respond rapidly to present trends, and foresee future changes. Similarly, employees think that the university's capacity for comprehension, response, and anticipation of future demands has a substantial impact on their involvement. Additionally, the university's capacity for fostering innovation, learning, and skill development improves worker engagement. Multiple regression analysis's findings, however, show that consistency had a detrimental and statistically insignificant impact on workers' involvement. Therefore, the university must be flexible while still upholding a strong corporate ethos. As a result, given the results of this study, it can be said that corporate ethos plays a substantial role in enhancing workers' engagement, as demonstrated by the statistically significant contributions of flexibility and involvement to workers' engagement. Consistency has a negative but statistically insignificant impact on employee engagement, whereas the mission has a positive but statistically insignificant impact. In summary, we can say that not all corporate ethos measures significantly affect employee engagement.

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